

KNOWLEDGE
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Reducing women's inequalities in EU Agricultural Areas: the role of digitalisation

HIGHLIGHTS REPORT

22 OCTOBER 2024

On October 22, the [European Association for Innovation in Local Development \(AEIDL\)](#) hosted a CODECS webinar on [Reducing women's inequalities in EU Agricultural Areas](#), exactly one week after the [International Day of Rural Women](#). The event brought together a diverse range of experts and stakeholders to discuss the critical role of gender in agriculture and rural areas, with a particular focus on how digitalisation can contribute to reducing inequalities.

The conversation featured insights from experts and innovators discussing challenges and opportunities related to gender equality in agriculture and the impact of digital tools. The webinar explored the current state of women in agricultural systems, highlighted the need for policy changes to support women's participation in the sector, and examined strategies to ensure that technology is accessible and inclusive for women. The webinar showcased case studies of women-led innovations in agriculture and encouraged collaboration between stakeholders to create a more equitable and sustainable future.

Blanca Casares, Policy expert at AEIDL, opened the session emphasising the timeliness of the event in light of ongoing political momentum at both European and national levels to advance gender equality. She pointed out that sectors like agriculture, where gender disparities remain significant (i.e. land ownership, access to resources, and decision-making power), are now at a crucial juncture, with new EU policies and technological advancements creating an opportunity to address these structural inequalities in a comprehensive and sustainable way.

ORGANISER:

22 OCTOBER 2024

ONLINE

80 PARTICIPANTS

(research, public authorities, advisors, business, producers, other EU-funded projects, etc.)

26 COUNTRIES

PRESENTATIONS AND RECORDINGS [HERE](#)

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If you see this icon, click to see the presentation

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Assesing the social and benefits of digitalisation

Gianluca Brunori

Full Professor, University of Pisa & CODECS Coordinator

Gianluca Brunori, CODECS Coordinator from the University of Pisa, opened the session with a speech outlining the project's objectives in driving digital transformation within farming systems. He emphasised CODECS's focus on assessing the social and economic costs and benefits of digitalisation, and highlighting that gender is a crucial aspect to consider. Professor Brunori underscored the importance of incorporating gender considerations into digitalisation strategies, noting that these are however often overlooked.

In what ways can digitalisation contribute to promote gender equality? And to what extent women can be drivers of a sustainable digitalisation?

With presentations and insights from multiple stakeholders, including experts in the field as well as women entrepreneurs in the agritech sector, the session aimed to deepen our understanding of the key role digitalisation plays in women empowerment.

He closed his speech with key questions to guide discussions on digitalisation and gender issues: How does digitalisation contribute to gender equality or inequality?

Gender equality in rural areas and agriculture: Current status and future directions

Tacko Ndiaye

Rural Transformation and Gender Equality Division at the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO)

The session continued with a presentation from Tacko Ndiaye, team leader at FAO's Rural Transformation and Gender Equality Division, who shared insights from the 2023 report on the [Status of Women in Agrifood Systems](#).

Status of women in Agrifood systems

Mrs Ndiaye presented key data on the role of women in agrifood systems (AFS) worldwide. Globally, 36% of working women and 38% of working men are employed in agrifood systems. In low- and middle-income countries, agrifood systems provide livelihoods for a larger share of women than men, agrifood systems are a greater source of livelihoods for women than for men, with 66 % of working women in sub-Saharan Africa and 71% in Southern Asia employed in AFS. In Europe and North America, this figure stands at 42%.

Figure 1. FAO (2023)

However, despite women's significant contribution to agrifood systems, their roles are often marginalised and their **working conditions** poorer than men's. Women's work in AFS is largely more irregular, informal, low-skilled, labour incentive, often offering limited or no social protection. Furthermore, women in agrifood systems are more likely to be employed part-time.

Additional challenges persist: female-managed farms produce 24% less than male-managed farms of comparable size, and a **gender pay gap** remains, with women earning 82 cents for every dollar men earn. Women's **access to essential resources and assets**, such as digital technology, land, financing, and services, also lags far behind men's access.

Furthermore, gender inequality in agrifood systems is closely intertwined with **climate vulnerability**. Female-headed households, for example, are more susceptible to the impacts of heat stress and flooding than male-headed households, which further deepens existing gender inequalities. [The Unjust Climate](#) (FAO, 2024) report found that a 1% increase in average temperature leads to a 34% income loss for female-headed households, compared to male-headed households.

Policy needs to empower rural women

Mrs Ndiaye highlighted key policy recommendations to empower women in agrifood systems:

1. **Gender-transformative approaches**, to change discriminatory norms at local level.
2. **Closing gaps in land tenure** can boost employment, investment, natural resource management, access to services, resilience, food security, and reduce gender-based violence.
3. **Access to formal childcare** has a large positive impact on mother's employment and returns in agrifood systems

4. **Group based approaches** are important for increasing women's empowerment and resilience.

5. **Social protection** can enhance women's employment opportunities and enhance resilience.

She outlined specific call to actions to empower women and strengthen their resilience in agricultural contexts, highlighted that in light of the presentation from Prof Brunori, these actions can be applicable to digitalisation. These actions include: (1) investing in high-quality research and data disaggregated by sex, age and other dimensions of social and economic differentiation; (2) Intervening at scale using proven approaches which close asset and resource gaps; (3) Using intentional interventions focusing on empowerment.

The role of digitalisation

The agricultural sector is rapidly digitising, evolving from using digital tools for information dissemination to full digitalisation of the agricultural ecosystem. Digitalisation can promote gender equality in AFS by addressing barriers that hinder women's participation in value chains and providing new channels for socio-economic empowerment.

However, while digital tools are proliferating, systemic and structural barriers to access them and adoption remain significant for many women. Policy measures and targeted programs focused on equipping rural women with digital literacy and skills are rare but essential. Digitalisation could close gender gaps in access to resources such as advisory services, business training, markets, and finance, ultimately enhancing women's livelihoods and empowerment in the agrifood sector. Digital inclusion can be achieved by providing offline participation options, adopting gender- and marginalised group-responsive digitalization practices, and actively addressing digital divides.

Gender in digitalisation of agriculture

Blanca Casares

European Association for Innovation in Local Development (AEIDL)

Blanca Casares presented an overview of AEIDL's work on gender mainstreaming in rural development. She introduced two policy briefs '[The role of women in rural development and innovation](#)' and '[Women for a sustainable future of rural areas](#)', highlighting women's critical roles in fostering innovation and sustainability in rural communities.

She emphasised the political landscape supporting gender mainstreaming in EU policies, which can drive sustainable digitalisation. She highlighted key policies, including the [Path to the Digital Decade](#), [CAP National Strategic Plans](#) (launched in January 2023 to tailor EU member states' implementation of CAP objectives), the [European Data Strategy](#), and the [Strategic Dialogue for the Future of Agriculture](#) report (September 2024).

She shared findings from the Horizon 2020 project [DESIRA](#) (Digitisation: Economic and Social Impacts in Rural Areas, 2019-2023), coordinated by the University of Pisa. DESIRA advocated to streamline digital competences adapted to different groups in rural areas, to promote innovation and digital ecosystems and to support data-driven decisions. In DESIRA, the gender dimension was worked on with the Living Labs in a project led by the James Hutton Institute. Among the main findings, the following stand out:

- The Living Labs (LLs) presented varied perspectives on the national and broader context of digitalisation, noting some gendered dynamics.
- Some LLs observed a slight gender imbalance in their composition, but this did not affect the level or type of participation from either gender.
- Other LLs shared data on men's and women's participation in online activities, noting only slight differences.
- LLs reflected that their thematic focus sometimes influenced gender participation levels. For instance, in Andalusia, where forest fires and digitalization are male-dominated sectors, the LL actively sought to include more women. In Croatia, the DigiFarm Tour had a higher representation of women, reflecting the prominence of women in civil service roles in that region.
- When collecting national-level information, some LLs found reports with gender-specific data, while others encountered limited gender-disaggregated information.

These findings suggest that in DESIRA, the gender divide in digital skills is nuanced and women often utilised digital tools for small farms and rural enterprises.

Mrs. Casares also discussed findings from [GRASS CEILING](#), Horizon Europe project (2022-2025) which stands for Gender Equality in Rural and Agricultural Innovation Systems.

The GRASS CEILING project promotes rural women-led socio-ecological innovations across nine Living Labs in

various European countries. The project aims to enhance understanding, awareness, and recognition of women's contributions to rural development. Its objectives include transforming gender norms and stereotypes, improving policy and Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) tools, and strengthening women's capacity to drive innovation in rural communities.

AEIDL's role includes **co-creating policy recommendations and tools to support women's contributions to sustainable rural and agricultural development**. The [European Policy Forum for Women-Led Innovation](#), co-led by AEIDL, engages external experts to review and refine the project's policy outcomes. This will help ensure consider how our results can be extrapolated to the EU level and whether they may be turned into actionable policy recommendations, hence enhancing their applicability across the EU. AEIDL also launched a [community group within the Rural Pact for rural women](#).

As part of GRASS CEILING, an inception report was prepared, and will be made public in the coming months. The report includes:

1. A historical review of gender equality in European politics and its global action
2. An assessments of current gender equality strategy 2020-2025
3. Gender considerations in policies linked to agriculture, rural and regional development
4. What is expected from now: The Union of Equality

Mrs. Casares concluded with several **opportunities to advance gender equality in rural areas**. She stressed the importance of integrating gender mainstreaming into policies and regulations, producing gender-disaggregated data, and conducting comparative studies on rural women across Europe. This approach will ensure a more inclusive understanding of their unique challenges and opportunities, supporting the development of targeted solutions.

To support rural women across Europe, improving infrastructure and services in rural areas is essential. By leveraging newly arrived broadband connectivity, rural communities can reduce precarious employment, promote generational renewal, and encourage innovation and entrepreneurship among rural women. Additionally, actively involving women in decision-making processes is vital to fostering equality and sustainable development in these communities.

Furthermore, to empower rural women, it is crucial to facilitate access to credit, adapt taxation while targeting advisory services if needed. Expanding access to new markets, building networks, and forming collaborations are also key. Finally, offering flexible work options, including support for families and childcare providers, will further strengthen rural women's participation and economic resilience.

Case studies on women-led innovations in agriculture

The second half of the webinar showcased inspiring case studies of women-led innovations in agriculture.

Mary Grace Gasco
SpaceCrop

Mary Grace Gasco, founder of [SpaceCrop](#), presented how her company uses satellite data and Artificial Intelligence to help farmers manage irrigation more efficiently. SpaceCrop's technology offers a solution through "smart irrigation farms" that use customised SaaS platforms to monitor soil moisture and weather forecasts. Through weekly SMS updates, farmers receive critical data on soil and weather conditions, allowing them to make more informed and timely decisions on their farming practices.

Mrs Gasco highlighted SpaceCrop's successful implementation of this technology in Hungary, where it demonstrated reductions

of up to 30-40% in water and energy use and increase of up to 50% in crop productivity when combined with precision irrigation.

The company is now looking to expand these pilot projects with farms that require frequent irrigation and potentially use Internet of Things (IoT) devices to enhance data validation. Through partnerships, SpaceCrop Technologies aims to improve irrigation practices, increase resilience to extreme weather and support global food security efforts. in the value chain, bridging producers and consumers.

Saša Kržič
Mikrozelenje Šebenik

Saša Kržič, FLIARA ambassador, shared her journey in developing [Mikrozelenje](#), an e-commerce platform for her micro-greens and dried flowers business, which allowed her to expand her reach to a broader customer base.

The COVID-19 pandemic drove her to innovative, leading her to develop a more resilient business model, including a new e-commerce platform to sell growing kits, seeds, and tools directly to customers, and helping people grow microgreens at home. This digital pivot transformed the business, making it the largest microgreens provider in Slovenia and increasing its market reach beyond local restaurants.

Through her e-commerce platform, Mrs Kržič has connected with international customers, all while supporting her local rural community by creating jobs. Despite growth, Sasha faces challenges, including navigating complex bureaucratic processes to secure funding and reliable suppliers.

She expressed pride in her company's local impact and was recently recognised for her work as a "flower farmer". She concluded by highlighting her commitment to sustainable growth, underscoring the value of digitalisation in overcoming geographic and logistical barriers to connect with global consumers.

Panel discussion: challenges and opportunities for rural women – with Maura Farrell (FLIARA Coordinator), Mary Grace Gasco

(SpaceCrop), Saša Kržič (Mikrozelenje Šebenik), Tacko Ndiaye (FAO), Lorena van de Kolk (Gender Alliance for Innovation in Agriculture); moderated by Blanca Casares (AEIDL)

The final segment featured a panel discussion with Tacko Ndiaye (FAO), Mary Grace Gasco (SpaceCrop) and Saša Kržič (Mikrozelenje), joined by **Maura Farrell**, coordinator of **FLIARA** (Female-led Innovation in Agriculture and Rural Areas) and **Lorena van de Kolk**, founder of the Gender Alliance for Innovation in Agriculture. Together, they explored the challenges and opportunities for rural women, sharing their expertise and experiences.

The discussion emphasised the vital role that women play in the agricultural sector and the need for intentional efforts to empower them through innovative solutions. **Mary Grace** and **Saša Kržič** opened the dialogue by sharing insights from their respective experiences, highlighting the importance of integrating gender perspectives into agricultural innovation. They stressed that women's participation in agriculture is not **only a matter of equity but also essential for achieving food security and economic development**.

Maura Farrell, representing the **FLIARA** project, highlighted key ideas on how to bridge the digital and policy gaps for women in rural and agricultural settings. She stressed that policy gaps, especially in rural broadband and digital infrastructure, significantly hinder women's access to the necessary digital resources. She noted that digital literacy remains a challenge, in part due to the **historical under-representation of women in STEM**. Mrs Farrell advocated for gender-tailored digital literacy programmes from an early age to encourage greater participation in agricultural technology. In addition, she noted that women often have difficulty accessing advisory services and funding for digital tools, as exemplified by a young female farmer she interviewed, who had more difficulty securing funding than implementing digital solutions. Maura suggested the need for inclusive **policy assessments to ensure accessibility to digital solutions** and urged consideration of **microfinance options to better support women in rural agricultural entrepreneurship**. Maura stressed the need to strengthen the design of Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) interventions in the current Strategic Plans and the possibility of monitoring their progress in order to know which measures are being effective.

Lorena van de Kolk emphasised the need to include women in decision-making within agriculture and agri-tech, noting that despite their involvement at the grassroots level, women often remain absent from high-level positions. She highlighted barriers such as **imposter syndrome, work-life balance and structural exclusions**, and advocated for policies that actively integrate women into the leadership of agricultural agencies and startups.

Mrs van de Kolk also underscored the value of networking between farmers and tech companies, enabling experience-sharing, collaborative discussions, and visibility for innovative projects to foster a sense of community. She stressed the importance of

mentoring and female role models to guide young women in this male-dominated field. To challenge stereotypes and inspire more women to join the field, she advocated for increased communication about women's success stories in agriculture and agri-tech (for examples, via social media or podcasts).

Additionally, she suggested that the **EU's 'Women on Boards' Directive could inspire similar action**, although it currently excludes smaller companies. Finally, she highlighted the importance of training and education at an early stage, ensuring the transfer of knowledge and experience to newer generations to prevent the repetition of gender disparities and cultivate a passion for both farming and technology among young women.

Moreover, **Tacko Ndiaye** highlighted the urgent need to improve digital literacy and women's access to technology, especially in rural areas, and underlined that scalable solutions are essential to make a significant impact. She emphasised that digital platforms offer women greater access to resources, market information and financial services, but broader sectoral reforms and gender-sensitive policies are needed. She called for an inclusive approach, with women **actively involved in the co-design of technologies** to ensure their relevance and accessibility. She also noted that while some countries set gender targets in broadband policies, broader efforts are needed to remove barriers that prevent women from adopting technology, especially in agriculture.

In addition, the panellists highlighted the importance of including a **gender perspective in agricultural technology development**. **Mary Grace Gasco** highlighted how collaboration with diverse stakeholders enabled her team to redesign their agricultural technology to better meet the needs of women farmers after discovering gaps in women's participation in their target regions. This led them to refine their approach, considering gender-specific challenges and adapting their technology solutions to ensure they effectively supported women's role in farming households.

Furthermore, **Tacko Ndiaye and Maura Farrell** highlighted the need for women-specific technology tools, digital literacy and training initiatives to address the gender gap. They cited the need for technology companies to **design tools that consider the specific needs of women**, from digital literacy programmes to context-specific tools, such as the 'talking books' used in Uganda to raise awareness of women's land rights. These efforts are essential for equitable access to **agricultural technology and for policy frameworks such as the CAP to enforce gender mainstreaming at national and EU level**.

Next steps: CODECS Knowledge Accelerator

Merveille Ntabuhashe

Project Manager, European Association for Innovation in Local Development (AEIDL)

Presentations and discussions during the event underscore the critical importance of women in agriculture and the urgent need for collective action to empower them through innovation, policy reform, and cultural shifts.

In closing, Merveille Ntabuhashe from AEIDL introduced the CODECS Knowledge Accelerator Community, a network aimed at fostering discussions, collaboration and knowledge exchange among stakeholders in the agriculture and digitalisation sectors. Interested actors can join the KA Community to stay informed about upcoming activities here.

Figure 2. CODECS Knowledge Accelerator

